

Evaluation of a Novel Posture in Betterment of Ergonomics in Laproscopic Appendectomy in Sitting Posture

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Abstract:

Background: Laparoscopic surgery poses ergonomic challenges for surgeons, potentially leading to musculoskeletal issues. This study evaluates the ergonomics of laparoscopic appendectomy performed in a sitting posture compared to the standard standing position.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted on 30 patients diagnosed with appendicitis from June 2022 to March 2024. Laparoscopic appendectomies were performed with the surgeon in a sitting position. Ergonomic factors, surgical outcomes, and surgeon comfort were assessed.

Results: The mean age of patients was 30 ± 5 years, with 60% males and 40% females. The mean BMI was 24 ± 4.2 kg/m². 83.3% presented with acute appendicitis and 16.66% with subacute appendicitis. The mean operative duration was 35 ± 10 minutes. Surgeons reported neck pain in 26.6% of cases, headache in 20%, shoulder pain in 20%, and eye strain in 13.3% of cases. No lower back, knee, ankle, elbow, wrist, or finger pain was reported. 90% of procedures were performed smoothly, with no open conversions. All surgeons (100%) adapted easily to the novel posture.

Conclusion: The sitting posture for laparoscopic appendectomy demonstrated improved ergonomics compared to the standing position, with minimal musculoskeletal issues reported. The technique showed a favorable learning curve and did not compromise surgical outcomes or duration.

Keywords: Laparoscopic Appendectomy, Ergonomics, Sitting Posture, Surgical Technique, Musculoskeletal Disorders.

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Introduction

Acute appendicitis is the most common emergency in abdominal surgery [1]. The Disease appendicitis is known from 16th century & was called peri-typhilitis. In the year 1889, Mc Burney described its clinical features & evolution of the disease. Laparoscopic surgery is considered as key milestone in the minimally invasive surgery. Laparoscopic appendectomy was first performed by Semm in the year 1982. Laparoscopic surgery has improved the patient's recovery time & enhanced the quality of surgery when compared to open procedure. Laparoscopic surgery has advantage of less pain, less wound complications with early enhanced recovery with short hospital stay, less morbidity & better cosmetic results [2, 3]. The laparoscopic surgery has a disadvantage of lack of tactile sensation & binocular vision [4, 5].

There is restriction of degree of freedom in laparoscopic surgery which has resulted in straining,

resulting in musculoskeletal fatigue of the operating surgeon [4, 5]. This can be overcome by better ergonomics [6]. The "ergonomics" is defined as "the concept of arranging working environment to fit the worker, instead of pushing the worker to fit the environment" [7].

Ergonomics are a big challenge in conventional MIS, with a main issue remaining the disassociation between the visual and the working field. The strain on the surgeon due to operation theatre arrangements, instrument structure, operating table height, monitor position, etc. has a significant effect on the outcome of MIS in general [8].

In addition, the evaluation of stress and strain to surgeons during MIS procedures is still technically very challenging. It is thus important that the awareness about these ergonomic challenges that MIS surgeons are facing today are addressed properly and serve as a basis [8].

In our study, we mainly focus on ergonomics of laparoscopy appendectomy in sitting posture compared to routine standing posture. There are limited studies available regarding laparoscopic ergonomics in sitting posture.

Aims & Objectives:

- 1) The aim of our study is to evaluate the ergonomics in laparoscopic appendectomy in sitting posture.
- 2) To evaluate learning curves of laparoscopic appendectomy in sitting posture.

Materials and Methods

The source of data for this study were patients admitted under the General Surgery Department at SSIMS & RC Davangere from June 2022 to March 2024. A total of 30 patients diagnosed with appendicitis were included in the study. Patients were taken up for the laparoscopic appendectomy after taking the informed written consent for the study.

For the methodology, the study employed a prospective observational design.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age >18 years
- Sex – Both male and female
- Diagnosed with acute and subacute appendicitis clinically or sonographically
- BMI

Exclusion Criteria

- Appendicular abscess
- Appendicular perforation
- Appendicular mass
- Who had contraindications for laparoscopic surgery

Patient data (age, sex, and complaint) were recorded.

Other data as comorbidities, BMI, operative time, simple or difficult case, hospital stay, and postoperative outcomes also were noted.

Procedure

- All the patients diagnosed with appendicitis, after

applying inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. The diagnosis of appendicitis was confirmed with the radiological investigation.

- Routine lab investigations were done.
- Written and informed consent was taken for surgery. Anaesthesiologist fitness for surgery was taken. All the patients were administered cefoperazone & sulbactam along with proton pump inhibitor preoperatively.
- Patient was induced with general anaesthesia. After induction of anesthesia, Patient was catheterised under all aseptic precautions. Abdominal wall is painted using antiseptic solution, and draped. Abdominal examination was done under anesthesia to rule out appendicular mass.
- In our study, 10 mm umbilical port is inserted by open technique & pneumoperitoneum is created using CO₂ with a flow rate of 6l/min and at a pressure of 12mmhg. Two 5 mm working ports were inserted under vision. Putting the table in the Trendelenburg position and tilting up the right side were taken to benefit from the gravity to take bowel and omentum away from the operative field. Height of the Table is adjusted as per operating surgeon's convenience.
- Operating surgeon sits on a chair on the left side of the patient. Assistants standing beside the operating surgeon. Monitor is placed towards the right side of the Operating table and adjusted as per operating surgeon's convenience.
- Instruments are inserted into working ports. Azimuth angle and elevation angles were measured intraoperatively. Images captured from video records of each operation were used to measure manipulation angle.
- Appendix identified and intraop findings noted. Mesoappendix is separated using bipolar energy source. Adhesions if noted are released. Appendectomy procedure was done, appendix specimen is retrieved through umbilical port. Any complications, operating time, blood loss are noted.
- Ports are removed, gas desufflated. Ports closed in surgeons standing posture. No intraop and immediate post op complications related to operating surgeons posture noted. Post surgery the operating surgeon is given questionnaires.

Table 1: Showing Questionnaires to operating surgeon

Sl. No	Questionnaire	Yes/No
1	Eye straining	
2	Headache	
3	Lower Backache	
4	Knee or ankle pain	
5	Shoulder pain	
6	Elbow pain	
7	Wrist pain	

8	Thumb and other fingers pain	
9	Ease of the adaptation of surgeon to the novel posture	
10	Any additional surgical complications occurred due to novel posture	
11	Conversion to open surgical procedure	

Statistical Analysis: Statistics were considered significant if $P \leq 0.05$. As AUC 0.7 was regarded as good, the ROC curve was also utilized to calculate the AUC, sensitivity, and specificity of all markers.

Table II: Showing statistical analysis

Patients	N=30
Age (Mean \pm SD)	30 \pm 5
Sex Male N (%)	18 (60%)
Female N (%)	12(40%)
BMI	24 \pm 4.2
Mean \pm SD	Kg/m ²
Presentation	
Acute Appendicitis N (%)	25(83.3%)
Subacute appendicitis N (%)	5(16.66%)

Results

This prospective observational study involving 30 patients is conducted over a period of 18 months in the Department of General Surgery SSIMS & RC Davangere.

The mean age of the patients is 30 \pm 5 years, 18 males (60%) & 12 females (40%) with mean BMI 24 \pm 4.2 kg/m², 25(83.3%) presented with acute appendicitis and 5(16.66%) with subacute appendicitis.

- Overall duration of study was similar to the standard lap appendectomy.
- No new surgical complications noted in sitting posture.
- Out of 30 cases performed by the surgeons, Surgeons had neck pain in 6 cases. None of them complained of any other physical complaints like eye straining, back pain, knee or ankle pain, shoulder pain, elbow pain, wrist pain, thumb and other fingers pain.

Table III: Showing questionnaire with their results

Questionnaire	RESULTS
Eye straining N (%)	04 (13.3%)
Headache N (%)	06 (20%)
Neck pain N (%)	08 (26.6 %)
Shoulder pain N (%)	6 (20%)
Lower Backache N (%)	0 (0%)
Knee or ankle pain N (%)	0 (0%)
Elbow pain N (%)	0 (0%)
Wrist pain N (%)	0 (0%)
Thumb and other fingers pain N (%)	0 (0%)
Any additional surgical complications occurred due to novel posture N (%)	Nil
Ease of adaptation of surgeon to the novel posture N (%)	4 (100%)
Learning curve N (%)	4 (100%)
ERGONOMICS	RESULTS
Operative duration Mean \pm SD	35 \pm 10 mins
Feasibility of procedure Smooth performance N (%)	27 (90%)
Struggling N (%)	3(10%)
Open conversion N (%)	0(0%)

Discussion

Our study aim is to evaluate the ergonomics in laparoscopic appendectomy in sitting posture & to evaluate learning curves of laparoscopic appendectomy in sitting posture.

1. In a study conducted by Lujain Alshareef *et al.*, Cureus in 2023 in Saudi Arabia showed that surgeons have high level of neck and back pain. In this study the prevalence of back, neck and shoulder pain among the studied surgeons was 68.2%, 56.9% & 46.2% respectively, while the

overall prevalence of musculoskeletal problems was 87.2% [9].

2. In a study conducted by R Bergueret *et al.*, in 1997, "A comparison of surgeons posture during laparoscopic and open surgical procedures" concluded that surgeons exhibit decreased mobility of the head and back and less anteroposterior weight shifting during laparoscopic manipulations despite a more upright posture. This more restricted posture during laparoscopic surgery may induce fatigue by limiting the natural changes in body posture that occur during open surgery [10].
3. In a study conducted by Margareta WärénStomberg *et al.*, in 2010 concluded that, the laparoscopic technique often requires static and tiring work positions, sometimes extreme, which can explain musculoskeletal disorders among general surgeons and gynaecologist [11].
4. In a study conducted by Tegan Thurston *et al.*, in 2022 concluded that Surgeons developed fatigue in consecutive cases while performing minimally invasive surgery (MIS). HE surgeons demonstrated a lower overall physical workload while also demonstrating different patterns in muscle work. The findings from this study can be used to inform further ergonomic studies and the data from this study can be used to develop surgical training programs focused on the importance of surgeon ergonomics and minimizing occupational injury risk [12].
5. In a study conducted by AmeerAlhusuny in 2021 concluded that Several factors in the workplace environment (temperature, asymmetrical weight bearing and forward head movement) and individual (being female and

wearing vision correction glasses) were significantly associated with neck/shoulder problems and visual symptoms. Evaluation of different strategies to minimize the strain on the neck/shoulder region and the visual system is required [13].

Reviewing the literature for different postures in laparoscopic surgery showed, no novel posture even though there is high incidence of musculoskeletal problems in erect posture of surgeon.

In our study sitting posture of a surgeon had better ergonomics with minimal musculoskeletal problems.

The surgeon adapted well to the novel posture with minimal difficulties (easy learning curve). No surgical complications related to this novel posture were noted.

Ergonomic adjustments for laparoscopic surgery [8]

Goal of proper posture:

- 1) Comfort
- 2) Efficiency of movement
- 3) Minimization of musculoskeletal injuries

Determinants of ideal posture [8]

- 1) Height of the OT table
- 2) Position of the visual display
- 3) Foot pedal locations
- 4) The selection of hand instruments

Insertion Angles in laparoscopic surgery [8]

Fig 1: Manipulation angle: Angle between two working instruments, ideal 45–75 degree [8]

Fig 2: Azimuth angle: Angle between one side instrument & telescope considered as a horizontal projection [8]

Fig 3: Elevation angle: Angle between the instrument and patient's body [8]

Limitations of the study:

1. Single institute study
2. Duration of the surgery is for 2 years
3. Patient's BMI correlation with ergonomics of the surgeon

Conclusion

On analyzing the observation in this study, it was noted that sitting posture had a better ergonomics in Laparoscopic appendectomy than in standing posture with similar duration of the procedure and easy learning curve.

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